

**22NRM03 “Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling
for heavy duty hydrogen transport”**

Report A1.5.2

Review of hydrogen venting systems and connections

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Summary

Hydrogen sampling systems usually have their own venting strategies mostly portable, which are developed specifically for each device. The design and parameters consider the properties of hydrogen such as its flammability, and the fact that it is prone to leaks.

This report reviews different mobile venting systems and connections based on the literature, on the activity A1.5.1, and on previous projects such as EMPIR JRP 19ENG04 MetroHyVe 2. General design aspects are described in this report and include the process parameters such as maximal pressure, peak flow, maximum or minimum temperature, and aspects related to weather considerations as well other risks such as air ingress.

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1 Introduction

The sampling of hydrogen fuel at a HRS is an operation within an explosive atmosphere (ATEX) area involving safety risks, which include a venting step. The sampling exercise is not part of the normal procedure that occurs at a HRS. In many cases, the sampling systems need to be purged several times with large volumes of hydrogen or at various locations of the sampling system. Therefore, an important aspect to consider is how to safely perform hydrogen venting at a HRS during a sampling event ((e.g. ATEX zoning, flow, pressure, height, authorisation). As HD-HRS operate at high flowrates and downtime has to be minimised (to reduce the impact on the refuelling of trucks), This aspect is exacerbated at heavy duty refuelling stations and safety is a key element for the standardisation of sampling. Hydrogen safety, particularly venting, is critical in preventing incidents related to pressure build-up, leaks, and hydrogen accumulation in unintended spaces. In activity 1.5.1, MetHyTrucks consortium reviewed the safety and venting requirements for the different hydrogen sampling strategies and investigated the connections used at the HD-HRS for venting and for safety.

This report reviews different mobile venting systems and connections based on the literature, on the activity A1.5.1, and on previous projects such as EMPIR JRP 19ENG04 MetroHyVe 2.

2 General aspects of venting

Vent systems are used to safely release hydrogen during normal and abnormal events (such as a sampling event) in order to reduce the effects of fire, asphyxiation, and fog on people, equipment, and the environment [1].

The design and design parameters (as example, vent diameter) must take into account the properties of hydrogen (for instance highly flammable, prone to leaks due to its small molecular size, less dense than air), the operations and process flow parameters (including maximal pressure, peak flow, maximum or minimum temperature. Typical equipment of a vent system can include pressure relief devices, purge and vent valves, bleed valves, exhaust stacks... [1].

2.1 General design aspects

The following aspects need to be considered when designing a venting system [1]:

- Pressure rating: it is a best practice to design the pressure rating of the piping at the highest rated pressure entering the vent systems
- Risk for plugging/blocking of the vent: the system shall be designed to avoid freezing (for example due to introduction of moisture (incl. weather protection, rain...)) or any obstruction
- Correct supports: especially for vent stacks, supports should withstand reaction forces (especially from pressure safety relief valve activating), local wind, and shall be designed for vent system expansion/contraction due to temperature changes.
- Risk for piping expansion/contraction due to temperature changes
- Correct temperature rating for joints or vent system
- Risk for air ingress (to be eliminated)

- Flow capacity and size of the vent system: designed for the maximum peak flow at the operating pressure
- Eventual interaction between flow streams (for example if sampling devices are flushed with nitrogen),
- Vent stack termination and release flow; vent stacks are used to move hydrogen away from ground level; they therefore should be designed to direct the flow of hydrogen vertical upward or angled outlet (0° to 90° from vertical) and to minimize reaction forces at the top of the vent stack. Several documents can be used as references for the vent stack design [2] [3].
- Other aspects to consider: flaring (only for steady flow), grounding (to minimize ignition sources), mufflers or silencers (usually not used)
- Deployment: vent systems should be easy to deploy, and shall not require complex adjustments at the refuelling station

2.2 Vent stacks

Vent stacks are used to safely disperse unused-unburned hydrogen. Vent stacks can be equipped with suitable burning systems. Vent stacks shall be designed and located to prevent exposure and lessen the effects of thermal radiation exposure to the supply system, personnel, and adjacent structures [2]. The vertical release of low-density hydrogen will aid in its dispersion and dilution in the atmosphere. If possible (this requires a steady flow), unused hydrogen can be flared. According to NASA guidelines, flaring may be considered for hydrogen vent rates greater than 0.2 kg/s [4]. [5]. Vent stack exits shall be elevated sufficiently to reduce thermal radiation doses to levels recommended in ANSI/API RP 521 [6], 3 m above grade, 0.61 m above adjacent equipment, or 1.5 m above rooftops.

Document CGA G-5.5 - Standard for hydrogen vent system shows an example of an acceptable hydrogen vent stack design (Figure 1, directly taken from the document) as well as an example of an improperly configured hydrogen vent stack design (Figure 2, directly taken from the document).

Figure 1. Example of an acceptable hydrogen vent stack design

Figure 2. Example of improperly configured hydrogen vent stack design

2.3 Prediction of hydrogen dispersion

Information about hydrogen dispersion can for example, be obtained by using model predictions.

A study by Shell Global Solutions and the Health and Safety Laboratory (HSL) [7] has compared real data obtained by carrying out controlled release experiments with release hydrogen pressures ranging between 10 and 150 bar with predictions from HGSYSTEM, a model developed and validated for jet releases of hydrocarbons. The agreement obtained was encouraging but in future work, it would be desirable to add the ability to model a release with a horizontal angle between the release and wind direction. The data model comparison could then be extended

3 Examples of venting systems and connections

The requirements for venting differ upon the design of the sampling systems. Hydrogen sampling systems have their own venting strategies (e.g. portable vent) which are developed specifically for each device. For example, some devices require a purge, other are designed to function without. Some systems use the vent of the HRS while others need a venting stack.

3.1 Venting systems used by the consortium

In activity A1.5.1 [7], a review of the current sampling strategies and venting of the devices developed or used by the consortium has been done. The information collected in the report A1.5.1 are briefly summarized below.

3.1.1 ENGIE device

All lines of the sampling device are connected with stainless-steel flexible hoses to a mobile vent system equipped with a 3.5-meter-high vent mast of a 1-inch stainless steel tubing (see Figure 3) equipped with a purge valve at the bottom to drain water if necessary.

Figure 3. Mobile vent mast of the ENGIE sampling device

3.1.2 NPL parallel sampling device

The NPL ParSam is a parallel sampling system. The portable vent has a full height of minimum 2.5m high. It is made of the section of stainless-steel connecting using quick connect. There is a small bend

just before the release point which is upward. The vent should be setup in a clear area at least 3 meters from sampler case, dispenser and FCEV. The connection to the sampling system is made using a flexible hose and quick connect to ensure perfect fit and no leak.

Figure 4. Mobile vent of NPL ParSam sampling device.

The system has no significant noise discomfort and is compatible with the pressure safety valve (PSV) specification (190 bar and flow up to 120 g/s). The ATEX zone at the outlet of the mobile vent are provided in Figure 4 in condition of PSV and normal purging operations.

Figure 4. Mobile vent of NPL ParSam sampling device and ATEX zone 2 created around the vent outlet. Distances are provided in mm based on different operation scenarios.

The zone above the mobile vent needs to be cleared up to 10 meters to ensure safe release of hydrogen. This is conservative estimate for the purge situation as the hydrogen supply is relatively small in volume (non-continuous and only the volume of the system which is estimated to less than 1 L).

3.1.3 NPL DirSam sampling device

The mobile vent is designed to ensure safe venting of the purged gas and from the pressure relief valve in case of emergency event. The system is connected to the sampling panel via a flexible hose. The vent is made of a combination of section of 1 meter of 3/4inch stainless steel pipe diameter with a tripod to maintain it. The system needs to be anchored to a solid structure or heavy load needs to be used on the feet of the tripod. The vent is assembled using quick connect to ensure perfect fit and no leakage on the vent line. The system is rated to the specification of the pressure relief valve (approximately 170 bar and flow up to 120 g/s).

The height of the mobile vent can be up to 4 meters with a bull horn outlet (not directed upstream but slightly horizontal). The direction of the outlet has raised concern as depending on the wind, portable alarms can pick up a signal on CO due to the hydrogen / CO interference on portable monitor alarms (GasAlert Quattro).

During operation, noise discomfort was reported especially for low flow, low volume (i.e., purging of sampling system).

3.1.4 Hy-SaM device

The system used a mobile vent of 3m height placed more than 5m away from anything (including the fuel dispenser) connected to the sampling system with a flexible stainless-steel hose (DN18 x 10 m). The procedure for venting is included in the general sampling procedure. It is also possible to vent the system with the central venting mechanism of the refuelling station.

3.1.5 H2 Qualitizer device (SINTEF, NPL)

The system does not require purging and is not filled with inert gas before use. The overall volume non vented by the H2 Qualitizer is expected to be approximately 20 ml with a maximum pressure of 160 bar as maximum pressure of the regulator and is purged by a bleed valve (Hoke with orifice 1 17/32 in full open). The venting and purging of the sampling system is realized through the HRS infrastructure except after the non-return valves. Pressure is vented through a hole drilled in the nut, angled back toward the body of the valve with the flow directed away from user (wearing protective clothing, especially goggles). The venting is not realised at 80 cm height from ground and 40 cm from the sampling cylinder valve. The safe release can only be realised at low flow rate to create a small ATEX zone of few dozens of centimetres. This approach was not considered good practice and would benefit from a better description of the vent zone (size, direction, bleed valve guidance on opening).

3.1.6 CESAME venting stack unit

CESAME's venting system is connected to the test unit via several flexibles as quick connectors with calibrated orifices (from 0.3 to 2 mm). The pressure in the tanks can go up to 700 bar, CESAME use a dual pressure reducer system with sonic nozzles to reduce the upstream pressure of the quick connectors under 400 bar. The maximal pressure of the flexible connected to the dual pressure reducer is 400 bar. Its length is about 1 m. This first flexible is connected to a second one via a screwed fitting, its maximal permissive pressure is 100 bar and its length is about 20 m.

Its outlet connected to the purging line via another rapid connector fitting. The purging mast, with a W shape (as shown in Figure 4), is fixed with quick connectors on a telescopic mast which can reach 4 m height. To reduce the acoustic radiated power, CESAME welded 2 tubes of 42 mm external diameter

(see the drawing in Figure 4) according to the Lighthill's analogy, 1952, which says that the hydrogen flow velocity is correlated to the power 8 ($p_a \propto v^8$). Moreover, to avoid any water stagnation inside the tube, a 2 mm diameter hole has been added at the bottom of the system.

Figure 4. CESAME venting stack unit – height = 4 meters

3.2 Other venting systems

A literature search has been conducted to find other venting systems. There are a lot of information available but very few is directly relevant to sampling devices and several companies can be approached for more specific applications. The list below is therefore non-exhaustive but proposes some solutions used for other applications than venting of sampling systems.

3.2.1 Esders Mobile Gas Flare

The company Esders [8] works in the field of gas measurement technology and gas leak detection and has technology for pipe system inspections, internal installation, gas pressure control systems or the pipe system. The company offers a product called Mobile Gas Flare with an integrated piezo igniter for safe and environmentally friendly flaring of natural gas, hydrogen or other combustible gases (see Figure 5), max. operating pressure 1 bar - max. flow rate approx. 40 Nm³/h methane at 1 bar.

The company also has other products such as a standpipe for professional pressure testing and for filling and emptying gas pipelines.

Figure 5. Mobile Gas Flare – 402380 (left) and standpipe (right)

3.2.2 Vehicles Portable hydrogen vent stack

Hydrogen in fuel cell electrical vehicles may need to be purged and some FCEV providers propose to use a so-called Portable Hydrogen Vent Stack. The particular vent stack has a T-top (see Figure 6). Unfortunately, we could not find any provider or more information about these products even with the references (FEFPVS (Honda) or HVS01 (Hyundai)).

Figure 6. Schematic of the portable hydrogen vent stack as described in the technical Service Bulletin of Hyundai [9].

3.2.3 Others

Some companies (Swagelok, Parker Hannifin Swagelok, WIKA and Hy-Lock) are developing hydrogen compatible components, in some cases specifically for heavy-duty or mobility applications [10] [11] [12] [13] that solutions for hydrogen venting (for example different types of valves). Discussions regarding specific application/design are encouraged by these companies.

3.3 Experimental testing of one venting condition

During the test campaign at ZBT in October 2024, Cesame implemented and tested its venting system (Figure 7). These tests were conclusive. All the safety requirements have been verified and validated. This system also meets the requirements of the noise radiated during operation, the efficiency and the robustness.

Figure 7. Extract from global P&ID of the Cesame mobile bench representing the venting system.

4 Conclusion

Hydrogen safety is critical at hydrogen refuelling stations. The sampling exercise is not part of the normal procedure at HRS (light-duty or heavy-duty). As HD-HRS operate at a high flowrate and the downtime in their operation has to be minimised, safety is a key element of the standardisation of sampling. Vent systems are used to safely release hydrogen during normal and abnormal events (such as a sampling event) in order to reduce the effects of fire, asphyxiation, and fog on people, equipment, and the environment and must be carefully designed with components rated with the applications.

Therefore, hydrogen sampling systems have their own venting strategies (e.g. portable vent) which are developed specifically for each device. The design and parameters must take into account the properties of hydrogen (for instance highly flammable, prone to leaks due to its small molecular size, less dense than air), and general design aspects which are described in this report (including for example the process parameters such as maximal pressure, peak flow, maximum or minimum temperature), weather considerations and different risks (air ingress...).

The review of the different systems highlights key aspect: noise, outlet design, ATEX zoning, stability of the vent, radius around the vent. The review highlighted the potential ATEX zone up to 10 meters above the release point and such calculation should be recommended for each portable vent based on their design (pipe diameter, outlet direction). The radius around the portable vent is most of the time 3 meters or more which may be challenging in some real-life conditions with small footprint HRSs close to the road and building for example. The novel strategy tested as flaring are an interesting alternative especially when the ATEX zone may be too large in some situations however it is not implemented in any sampling kit so far. The report emphasis the need for further activities, real life experience sharing and guidance for the safe deployment of sampling system for hydrogen fuel quality.

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